

GEOMETRIC AND MECHANICAL MODELLING OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

S. Rudov-Clark¹, S.V.Lomov², M. K. Bannister³, A. P. Mouritz¹, I.Verpoest²

¹*School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University,
GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, Victoria 3001, Australia*

²*Department of Metallurgy and Material Science, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven,
Kasteelpark Arenberg, 44, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium*

³*Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd., 226 Lorimer Street,
Fishermans Bend, Victoria 3207, Australia*

SUMMARY: This paper assesses the capability of the ‘*WiseTex*’ and ‘*TexComp*’ computer models developed at the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven to determine the fibre architecture and elastic properties of 3D woven fibre-polymer composites. The *WiseTex* model utilises minimum energy principles to predict the fibre architecture of textile preforms. In this paper the theoretical prediction of fibre architectures to various 3D orthogonal woven preforms using the *WiseTex* model are compared against the actual architectures of 3D woven fabrics. The resemblance of the theoretical to actual architectures is good, with the *WiseTex* model being capable of accurately determining the geometry and size of unit cells, areal density, fibre content and thickness of 3D woven fabrics. Reasons for any discrepancy between the *WiseTex* and actual fibre architectures are identified in the paper. The theoretical architectures of the preforms are then applied to the mesomechanical model - *TexComp* - to predict the elastic properties of 3D woven composites. Theoretical predictions of the in-plane Young’s modulus are compared against experimental modulus values for a variety of 3D woven fibreglass composites, and in general the agreement is good.

KEYWORDS: 3D textile composites, model, fibre structure, mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

3D woven fibre-polymer composites are gradually emerging as an alternative to traditional 2D laminates due to superior delamination toughness, better impact damage resistance and higher damage tolerance. In addition, the 3D weaving process provides a higher degree of automation and reduces lay-up time for thick composite components when compared to traditional prepreg manufacturing technology. 3D preforms can be woven into a wide variety of shapes allowing the production of composite structures such as I-beams or stiffened panels. 3D woven composites are used in aircraft and civil structures, and in the future may be used in ships, transportation and defence platforms [1].

The fabric preforms to 3D woven composites consist of multiple layers of warp and weft yarns interlaced by through-thickness binder yarns. Figure 1 shows the ideal fibre architecture of a 3D orthogonal woven preform, and it is seen the binder yarns extend in the through-thickness direction. Numerous studies have shown that the mechanical properties of 3D woven composites are highly dependent on the fibre architecture, which is determined by the weaving process [eg. 1]. However, the architecture can be altered inadvertently during weaving by crimping, misalignment and local changes in volume content of the in-plane yarns [2-4]. These changes to the fibre architecture can reduce the stiffness, strength, fatigue life and other in-plane mechanical properties of 3D woven composites [1-7]. Furthermore, the through-thickness yarns themselves can be distorted during weaving and the subsequent consolidation into a composite, and this may affect the delamination resistance and impact damage tolerance. Unfortunately, many micromechanical models for predicting the

mechanical properties of 3D woven composites assume an ideal actual fibre architecture, and do not consider microstructural features such as crimping, distortion and variations in local content of the load-bearing fibres. As a result, the theoretical estimation of the mechanical properties of 3D woven composites can be unreliable.

Figure 1: Idealised model of an orthogonal 3D woven preform.

A novel modelling approach has been developed at the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven to predict the elastic properties of textile composites. The approach basically involves modelling the geometric properties of the fibre architecture a textile preform using a computer model called ‘*WiseTex*’. This model uses minimum energy principles to predict the ‘real’ geometry of the preform, including such features as crimping, distortion and collimation of yarns and local changes in fibre content of the fabric [8]. Once the fibre architecture has been modelled, this information is used in the mesomechanical model known as ‘*TexComp*’ to predict the elastic properties of the consolidated textile composite [9,10]. This paper assesses the ability of the *WiseTex* model to predict the fibre architecture and the *TexComp* model to determine the in-plane Young’s modulus of 3D woven composites.

3D WOVEN PREFORMS AND COMPOSITES

The *WiseTex* and *TexComp* models were evaluated for a variety of 3D woven preforms and composites. The 3D preforms were woven into an orthogonal architecture from E-glass yarns using a computer-controlled Jacquard loom. The glass fibres had a Young’s modulus of 69 GPa, shear modulus of 30 GPa and Poisson ratio of 0.22. The ideal orthogonal architecture is depicted in Figure 1, and contains six layers of warp yarns and seven layers of weft yarns. Four different orthogonal architectures were woven by changing the binder path or linear density (or TEX) of the binder yarn. The differences between the 3D woven preforms are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Variations to the 3D woven preform fibre architecture.

	3D Preform Type A	3D Preform Type B	3D Preform Type C	3D Preform Type D
Binder Path	Over/under two surface weft tows	Over/under two surface weft tows	Over/under two surface weft tows	Over/under one surface weft tow
Density of binder yarn, TEX	68	204	408	68

The 3D woven preforms were consolidated with vinyl ester resin (Derakane[®] 411-C50 from Dow Chemicals) using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding. After moulding, the panels were held under pressure at a cure temperature of 110°C for one hour followed with a six hour post-cure at ambient temperature under platen pressure. The composites had an average

fibre volume fraction of 0.5, of which the warp fibre volume fraction comprises 0.23. The vinyl ester resin had a Young's modulus of 3.38 GPa, shear modulus of 1.2 GPa and Poisson ratio of 0.14.

WISETEX MODELLING

WiseTex is a textile geometry preprocessor for mechanical modelling of woven composites [8]. The function of the *WiseTex* model is to provide a readily available 'a priori' geometric modelling tool using input data from the manufacturer's fabric and yarn specifications. The geometry of the preform is calculated by considering the equilibrium of the yarn forces that are required to maintain a particular weave topology. These yarn forces include transverse forces generated by bending resistance and sliding friction between the yarns. The crimping and waviness of the warp and weft yarns is modelled using minimum energy principles, whereby the total bending energies of the yarns within a defined volume are considered simultaneously. The final cross-section shapes of the yarns are predicted using compressibility laws for the yarns.

To model the fibre architectures using *WiseTex* it is necessary to provide input data of the preform and fibre properties. The following information is required:

- TEX and fibre count of the yarns
- Coefficient of friction between the yarns, yarn compressibility and flexural rigidity or, alternatively, yarn dimensions measured within the fabric
- Diameter, tensile strength, Young's modulus and Poisson ratio of the fibres
- Number of warp/weft layers, yarn spacing and unit cell dimensions of the preform fabric.

Most of this information is readily obtained from data sheets and yarn supplier, however some data must be measured directly from the yarns and woven preform. In particular, if the law of yarn compression is not experimentally determined, then the compressed yarn dimensions d_1 and d_2 (defined in Figure 2) must be measured from samples of the composite. To this end, scanning electron micrographs taken of 3D woven composite samples were prepared and the yarn dimensions were measured using the image analysis software 'Scion Image'.

The unit cell is defined as the smallest repeating pattern that can be used to recreate the overall textile pattern of the preform. The unit cell dimensions for the 3D woven preforms were measured from scaled digital photographs. The geometrical input data for *WiseTex* modelling of the 3D woven preforms is given in Table 2.

Figure 2. Schematic of weft yarns showing D1 and D2 yarn dimensions

Table 2. Geometrical input data for *WiseTex* modelling

3D Preform	Yarn system	Yarns/cm	Linear density, TEX	d1, mm	d2, mm	Fibre diameter [⊗] , μm
A	Warp	2.05	1800	0.3	3.66	13
	Weft	1.78	2400	0.33	3.74	17
	Binder	2.05	68	0.1	0.74	9
B	Warp	1.41	1800	0.3	6.05	13
	Weft	1.90	2400	0.33	2.83	17
	Binder	1.41	204	0.2	1.45	9
C	Warp	2.42	1800	0.3	5.81	13
	Weft	2.04	2400	0.33	2.98	17
	Binder	2.42	408	0.23	1.65	9
D	Warp	1.35	1800	0.3	6.59	13
	Weft	1.82	1200	0.3	2.10	17
	Binder	1.35	68	0.2	0.71	9

[⊗]Data provided by Colan Industries Pty. Ltd.

Figure 3 shows the 3D geometry of a unit cell for the different 3D woven fabrics predicted using *WiseTex*. It is seen that the model can represent the complex fibre architecture of the preforms. Figure 4 shows the plane-view of the unit cell geometry determined using *WiseTex* superimposed on photographs of the 3D woven fabrics, and excellent agreement is observed. A further comparison of the predicted and actual 3D fabrics is given in Table 3, which compares calculated areal density and unit cell dimensions of the 3D woven preforms modelled using *WiseTex* against measured values. *WiseTex* is able to determine these parameters to within an accuracy of 10%, which demonstrates the model is able to predict the geometry of complex fibre architectures with good accuracy.

Table 3. *WiseTex* and measured values of the fabric weight and unit cell dimensions of the 3D woven preforms.

3D Preform	Preform areal density, g/m ²		Unit cell dimensions, mm			
	WiseTex	Measured	Parallel to warp		Parallel to weft	
			WiseTex	Measured	WiseTex	Measured
A	5235	5020	9.8	9.9	4.14	3.74
B	5525	5170	14.5	14.2	4.14	3.85
C	5823	5280	14.0	14.0	4.14	3.83
D	5287	5200	14.7	14.7	3.90	3.78

Figure 3. *WiseTex* models of a unit cell to the 3D woven fabrics. One tick on the scale equals 1 mm.

Using the measured values of the yarn dimensions, the *WiseTex* model can also predict the thickness and fibre volume fraction of textile composites. Table 4 compares the *WiseTex* and measured values for thickness and fibre content of the 3D woven composites, and again good agreement is observed. The *WiseTex* thickness values are slightly higher than the measured values, and this contributes to the theoretical fibre volume values being lower. It is believed that this small discrepancy is because of the effect of fibre nesting, which occurs in 3D woven fabrics, but was not considered when modelling the fibre architecture using *WiseTex* because the compressibility of the fabric and compression laws and flexural rigidity of the yarns were not known.

3D Preform A

3D Preform B

3D Preform C

3D Preform D

Figure 4. *WiseTex* and actual surface views of the 3D woven fabrics.

Table 4. *WiseTex* and measured values of thickness and fibre content of 3D woven composites

3D woven composite	Thickness, mm		Fibre volume fraction, V_f	
	<i>WiseTex</i>	Measured	<i>WiseTex</i>	Measured
A	4.14	3.74	0.498	0.524
B	4.14	3.85	0.526	0.527
C	4.14	3.83	0.553	0.541
D	3.90	3.78	0.534	0.539

TEXCOMP MODELLING

Using the theoretical model of the fibre architecture constructed using *WiseTex*, the elastic properties of the 3D woven composites were predicted using the *TexComp* model. Micromechanical calculations were performed using the ‘method of inclusions’ developed by Huysmans et al. [9,10]. The *TexComp* program reads the geometrical data computed by the *WiseTex* model, including information about the fibre structure of the yarns, fibre diameter, local fibre volume fraction inside the yarns, and mechanical properties of the fibres. Using the method of inclusions, *TexComp* computes the homogenised anisotropic stiffness matrix of the yarns from the properties of the fibres and polymer matrix. Then, according to the *WiseTex* description of the internal geometry, the yarns are subdivided into small elementary intervals, which are represented by elliptical inclusions, with their orientation corresponding to the local orientation of the yarn and stiffness matrix. The Mori-Tanaka theory is then applied to calculate the homogenised parameters of the unit cell of the composite.

The theoretical tensile properties predicted using the *TexComp* model were compared against experimental data for the 3D woven composites. Tensile tests on the composites were performed using square-sided specimens that were 25 mm wide with a gauge length of 120 mm [11]. The composites were loaded in the warp fibre direction at a crosshead rate of 0.1 mm/minute. Four tensile tests were performed on each of the 3D woven composites.

Table 4 compares calculated and measured values for longitudinal Young's modulus of the 3D woven composites. The agreement is good considering that the combined *WiseTex* and *TexComp* modelling approach does not consider all the microstructural features of 3D woven composites, such as variations in the waviness and crimp of load-bearing tows, nor the damage caused to tows during the weaving process, such as abrasion and breakage of fibres, that can affect the measured elastic modulus of the composite [12].

Table 5 lists the complete set of elastic properties for the 3D woven composites calculated using *TexComp*. Experimental research is in progress to measure these properties to evaluate further the accuracy of the *WiseTex-TexComp* modelling approach.

Table 4. Young's modulus values: measured and predicted using *TexComp*

3D Woven Composite	Young's modulus (E_{xx}) GPa		
	Calculated	Measured	% Difference
A	26.6	23.3±3.2	14
B	22.7	23.3±1.1	2.6
C	25.2	22.9±0.7	10
D	27.2	23.5±1.7	16

Table 5. Mechanical properties of the 3D woven composites predicted using *TexComp*

3D Woven Composite	E_{yy} , GPa	E_{zz} , GPa	G_{yz} , GPa	G_{xz} , GPa	G_{xy} , GPa	ν_{yz}	ν_{zy}	ν_{zx}	ν_{xz}	ν_{xy}	ν_{yx}
A	26.3	6.85	2.99	2.97	6.93	0.053	0.206	0.199	0.051	0.122	0.123
B	25.6	6.48	2.85	2.45	6.03	0.053	0.208	0.193	0.055	0.122	0.108
C	27.3	7.08	3.06	2.94	6.8	0.054	0.21	0.192	0.054	0.126	0.116
D	27.4	7.65	3.34	3.25	6.21	0.059	0.211	0.199	0.056	0.109	0.108

CONCLUSION

This study is a systematic evaluation of the combined *WiseTex-TexComp* modelling approach to predict the fibre architecture and mechanical properties of 3D woven composites. The modelling approach was tested for four types of 3D woven fibreglass composites with complex fibre structures. It was proven that the unit cell geometry, fabric density, fibre content and thickness of the 3D woven preforms can be accurately modelled using *WiseTex*. However, the *WiseTex* model does not readily determine local imperfections caused by the 3D weaving process, such as localised crimping of the in-plane yarns by the through-thickness reinforcement or variations in the waviness of the yarns. To model these parameters data such as flexural rigidity of the yarns and compressibility of the preform must be experimentally determined.

A preliminary assessment of the *TexComp* model revealed that the longitudinal Young's modulus of the 3D woven composites can be predicted with reasonable accuracy using the fibre architecture computed by the *WiseTex* model. Local imperfections in the fibre architecture that were not accounted for in the *WiseTex* model probably cause the relatively

small discrepancy between the measured and *TexComp* values for Young's modulus. Further validation of the *TexComp* model to predict other elastic properties of 3D woven composites is required, such as transverse and through-thickness Young's moduli, shear moduli and Poisson ratios. This research has progressed the potential use of the *WiseTex-TexComp* modelling approach to design composite structures using 3D woven composite materials.

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